

BOOK REVIEWS

Lake Erie and Lake St. Clair Handbook. Edited by Stanley J. Bolsenga and Charles E. Herdendorf. 1993. Wayne State University Press, Detroit, MI. 467 p. \$19.95 paper.

Occasionally a scientific volume is published that appeals to the layperson, teacher, and scientist alike and serves as a particularly valuable reference source. This book should prove to be such a volume. As the preface states, "The editors of this book have attempted to present a comprehensive view of the environmental quality and natural features of Lake Erie, Lake St. Clair and their environs" (p. ix). It "describes the conditions, processes, and natural features of the coastal and offshore waters of Lakes Erie and St. Clair, and the St. Clair, Detroit, and Niagara Rivers" (p. 3). The authors have taken on a rather formidable task and have excelled in producing a volume that could serve well as an introductory textbook for a survey course on this part of the Laurentian Great Lakes.

The book is organized into a brief introductory chapter followed by major chapters on the lithosphere (with subsections on physiography, bedrock geology, glacial geology, sediments and beach deposits, coastal processes, mineral resources, and natural features of special interest), atmosphere (climate, winds, solar radiation, severe weather), the hydrosphere (water levels and water budget, water temperature, currents, waves, storm surges and seiches, and ice), and the biosphere (lake ecology, physical, biological, and chemical structure of Lake Erie, lake flora and fauna, avifauna, and wild game). The biosphere chapter devotes forty-six pages to the origin, value, biota, and changes in coastal wetlands of the two lakes, with extensive descriptions of fifteen specific wetlands.

The editors compiled or wrote most of the material for the chapters and were assisted by Bonnie James (The Atmosphere), Theodore Ladewski (The Hydrosphere), Laura Fay (Water Chemistry), Jeffrey Reutter (Fishes), and Sandra Schuessler (Birds). The literature citations, including over 270 references, are followed by a handy twenty-page glossary and a detailed index. Several references on bird identification are buried within the text (pp. 329-330) rather than placed with the other references.

The broad title suggests that this book covers most topics of interest to most people. Certainly it covers a wide range of topics in varying detail. It focuses, however, on the natural history and ecology of these lakes, as opposed to their history of human use and abuse, and surprisingly little information is included regarding human impacts and environmental issues. For example, readers seeking knowledge of the history, extent, and trends of toxic substances in the lake sediments and waters will generally be disappointed; they will have to consult Burns (1985) and, for more current coverage of some impacts, recent special issues of the *Journal of Great Lakes Research* (e.g., Vol. 18(4) 1992, and Vol. 19(2) 1993) and other journals. The chapter on the hydrosphere lacks any mention of the controversial effects of icebreakers and the extension of the shipping season during periods of ice cover. Nor is water pollution discussed in that chapter. Mercury is the only major pollutant of the sediments and food web that

is presented in the chapter on the lithosphere (pp. 80, 82, 84). By reading the sections on fishes and avifauna, one would never be aware of the historical and continuing reproductive and physiological problems in these organisms caused by persistent toxic materials such as DDT, PAHs, and PCBs in several areas of Lake Erie and its connecting channels. Fortunately, an introduction to the effects of eutrophication and oxygen depletion is provided. Despite the tremendous impact created by the zebra mussel during its short tenure in lakes St. Clair and Erie, the index lacks reference to "zebra mussel," "exotic species," or "introduced species." I could find only a single short sentence (p. 286) which refers to the zebra mussel as simply a "new invader," with not even a figure provided. Perhaps the chapter on the biota was completed prior to the late 1980s, before its ecological and economic importance was realized. Otherwise, the omission of this organism, as well as the spiny water flea and other species that invaded in the last decade, is incomprehensible.

One of the more appealing aspects of the book is the inclusion of practical information. For example, the chapter on the atmosphere includes thunderstorm and tornado safety tips (pp. 159 and 163) and how to use marine wave and weather forecasting services (pp. 215-219). The best birding sites are described at length (pp. 331-355) in the avifauna section.

The editors have indeed assembled a wealth of useful information from widely scattered sources. Because they have presented most of this information in its original form, some inconsistency in the use of scientific units (e.g., Fahrenheit vs. Celsius, metric vs. British) occurs throughout. Textual descriptions of the various topics are in almost all cases illustrated by clearly printed and readily understandable drawings, graphs, or tables. These must be studied critically, however, because there are several errors. As examples: Figure 3.52 (p. 147) purports to show comfort zones for the eastern half of the U.S. in July but omits all of the eastern U.S. south of Missouri, Kentucky, and Virginia! Figure 4.18 (pp. 192-193) twice refers to the island region as eastern Lake Erie. In Figure 5.29 (p. 272) the plants labeled "floating plants" are really rooted floating-leaved plants as opposed to freely floating plants. In Figure 5.37 (p. 282) the two worms labeled as "sludge worm (oligochaete)" are oligochaetes, but neither of the species shown is found in areas of severe organic pollution where the sludgeworms thrive. As an important omission in Figure 5.53 (p. 377), swamp loosestrife (*Decodon verticillatus*) is shown, but the devastating purple loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria*) is neither shown nor listed in the index. It receives two sentences of text (p. 396).

Given its breadth of coverage, the *Lake Erie and Lake St. Clair Handbook* is well organized, informative, and enjoyable to read. It will probably receive frequent use as a regional reference to augment the standard limnology textbooks.

LITERATURE CITED

- Burns, N. M. 1985 *Erie the Lake that Survived*. Rowman and Allanheld Publishers, Totowa, NJ. 320 pp.

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